

An improved direct-rice seeder

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Transplanting, a highly labor-intensive and costly method, can be substituted by direct seeding, which could reduce labor needs by more than 20%. Rice is either dry-seeded on well-prepared, dry/moist soil or wet-seeded on puddled soil. Current direct-seeder models drill seeds continuously at a seed rate higher than recommended and without consideration of desired seed-to-seed spacing. As the seed drum is emptied, the seeding rate increases steadily and steeply at the end and uniformity in seeding rate is not maintained. Hence, an improved direct-rice seeder that uniformly distributes seeds will be more useful in maintaining a uniform plant population in the field.

A test rig was developed and the influence of the machine and operational parameters—drum shape, drum diameter, number of seed-metering holes, diameter of seed-metering holes, and forward speed of operation—on the seeding rate of the drum seeder were investigated under laboratory conditions. Optimum results were obtained with a hyperboloid drum 200 mm in diameter with nine seed-metering holes each 10 mm in diameter, and a forward speed of 1.0 kph.

The percent variation in seed discharge of the prototype drum was reduced when the drum was filled to half of capacity. Baffles inside the seed drum reduced the variation, resulting in a more uniform seeding rate. The optimized drum was assembled

to sow four, six, and eight rows of rice seeds and its field performance tested. It was found that the deviation from the recommended per-m² plant population using the prototype drum seeder was minimum, whereas the plant population was 2–4 times more with existing direct-rice seeders.

The prototype direct-rice seeders were tested with single

and double ground wheels with and without furrow openers and using dry and soaked seeds. The direct-rice seeder wheel with double ground wheels reduced the slip percentage from 14.4 to 9.4, but it had difficulty turning. The use of soaked seeds using the improved seeder with furrow opener resulted in a higher yield of grain and straw.

Field performance of the prototype direct-rice seeder and existing direct-rice seeder.^a

Parameter	Improved direct-rice seeder	Existing direct-rice seeder
Plant population (no. m ⁻²)	209	448
Tillers (no. m ⁻²)	500 (50 DAS) ^b 529 (75 DAS)	659 (50 DAS) 686 (75 DAS)
Productive tillers (no. m ⁻²)	376	467
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	126	96
Grain yield panicle ⁻¹ (g)	205	1.99
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.4	4.1
Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	6.0	4.9

^aValues indicate the maximum mean values of all treatments. ^bDAS = days after sowing.

Comparison of seed discharge with respect to time between existing and improved direct-rice seeder.

Crops sown with improved (top) and existing (bottom) direct-rice seeder.

Four-row improved direct-rice seeder.

Six-row improved direct-rice seeder.

Eight-row improved direct-rice seeder.

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